

POST-INDUSTRIAL SOCIETY: MEMORY, EMOTION AND TRANSFORMATION DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This main purpose of this paper is to contribute to the debate regarding the new roles of Design in face of the coming of post-industrial society and its changing values, emotional needs and understanding of quality of life. It sees Emotional Design as an approach that goes beyond to the physical properties of products to the emotional responses they evoke, the experiences they promote, the effects they have on society and the planet and, above all, the social transformations they help to shape.

Keywords: post-industrial society, transformation design, social memory, sociability, memorability.

INTRODUCTION

This main purpose of this paper is to contribute to the debate regarding the new roles of Design in face of the coming of post-industrial society and its changing values, emotional needs and understanding of quality of life. It sees Emotional Design as an approach that goes beyond to the physical properties of products to the emotional responses they evoke, the experiences they promote, the effects they have on society and the planet and, above all, the social transformations they help to shape.

It brings possible perspectives to be considered by designers, derived from a doctoral study on the relationship between affective memory and material things. It was organized in four sections. The first

brings fundamental concepts about the post industrial society and some thoughts about the new role of design; the second presents a brief view of the doctoral study “Memory Artifacts of Everyday Life: an interdisciplinary view on things that bring back good memories”; the third resumes the findings from the above mentioned study and the possible reasons why some things become “memorable” and introduces six promising perspectives or approaches to create memorable products derived from ongoing and continuous study within our research laboratory focusing the relationship between the designed world, memory and emotion. The fourth and last section brings our final considerations.

ON POST INDUSTRIAL SOCIETY AND THE NEW ROLE OF DESIGN

The activity of design was conceived at the birth of an industrial society and developed based on mass manufacturing and the production of tangible goods. However, today, the results from this practice are radically changing to a new paradigm. While the industrial society was based on materiality and goods manufacturing, the post-industrial society - as outlined by Daniel Bell (1974) in his book “The Coming of Post-Industrial Society” - will be information-led and service-oriented. The author emphasizes an increase of the service sector as one important characteristic of the post-industrial society and “a shift from an economy primarily based on goods production to one

based on services" (1974: 126). He adds that the post-industrial society is also marked by the "information sector", the centrality of human relationships and 'intellectual technology', based on information and computing technology.

According to Ronald Inglehart (1990, 2004) - coordinator of a world-wide survey of mass values and attitudes- the global economic development since World War II and the physical and economic security for individuals have changed their moral codes to what he named "post materialist values", including moral sentiments, self-esteem, self expression, trust in oneself and the group, collaboration, concerns with the environment, public morality, among others not related to material needs.

As observed by the sociologist Ulrich Beck (1998:21), "industrial society, understood as a model of the lifeworld (...) is disappearing" and although industrial production will continue, society are now much more conscious of their consequences and increasingly concerned not only about the quality of goods, but also about how they are produced and their effects on society and the planet. Samuel Bowles (2008) - PhD in Economics from Harvard University adds that "people act not only to acquire economic goods and services but also to constitute themselves as dignified, autonomous, and moral individuals".

In this context and not by chance Pine & Gilmore (1999) coined the term "experience economy" where the major economic offerings are not goods or services, but experiences. The authors observe that what we have calling post-industrial society also emphasizes personal experiences.

Among the key-values of the new emerging society we can also add a growing acceptance of and seek for spirituality; a collective consciousness based on global and local networks of information technology; a tolerance and even celebration of cultural, ethnic and

sexual diversity; ecological and social awareness and the idea that sharing and or using is better than owning.

In such a dematerialized economy and caring society the questions are: What kind of changes will occur to the design practice? Is it possible to think of a non industrial or a non object oriented design? Is there a new mental model adjusted to the post-industrial reality?

In an article suggestively entitled "The Dematerialization of Design", Jorge Frascara (2002) recognizes we are going through a moment of change and the need to redefine the objectives of design and its working methods. Exploring a contemporary notion of design, he suggests a shift of focus from objects, materials and production processes to the effects they will have on society and the planet, the context in which they will be used, as well as their consequences on people's daily life.

According to Frascara (2002:20) "Design is not concerned with objects, but with the impact that those objects have on people". The author also suggests a shift "from the design of objects to the design of situations and activities" or the "dematerialization of design".

Alexander Manu (in Bruinsma, 1995) astutely observed that "because designers create physical objects, they think of needs as having tangible shape. And product design tries to anticipate and meet the solid, mechanical needs of users". Max Bruinsma (1995), in his turn, argued that design needs a new mentality rather than new forms. Presenting what he called the "invisible side of design", Bruinsma warned that "giving form is not just clothing the object with a nice form, it is: giving form to the meanings that the object can assume, beyond its direct function".

In the same direction, Ezio Manzini (2004) asserts that the project's object becomes "an event oriented to a

result," indicating that "what is acquired is not a physical product, but an event that takes place in a certain place and at any given time and changes the status of the individual who acquired" hence "product-event should be seen as an artifact in four dimensions, where the fourth dimension is time". This change occurs through the interaction of several actors who cooperate to produce a certain value, and the events connected with this production value become the product of the design project.

The design's emancipation of the adjective "industrial" breaks new ground in the profession in the twenty-first century, enabling the activity to shape a variety of contemporary products (objects, and also not objects). Such as illustrated by Bertola (2004: 31) "product design goes to the design of the 'supply' system of a company, and ever more frequently to the design of life cycle of its offer, and also the dynamics of interaction between the user and product during use. It means that products design, today, includes services, experiences, environments, communications systems and other non tangible forms.

Mike Press and Rachel Cooper (2003) also explore the context, practices and the new roles of designers in post industrial times. For the authors, firstly, the essential characteristic of the designer is the fact that he was a maker. In other words, the activities and skills of making lies at the heart of the activity design. Secondly, design is a process of meaning-making: each object, communication or designed environment provides human experiences and they all carry meanings. By enabling meaning, the designer is a maker of culture, a cultural intermediary. Thirdly, the formation of the designer encourages creativity, originality and imagination, features highly valued in the post-industrial economy.

Recently, both companies and academia realized a potential for new approaches to design practice, which goes beyond the design of physical artifacts. John

Thackara (2008) points out a new path for the design: from the possession to the consumption of goods (i.e. from the property for the use of products). The author states that, for this to occur, we need a cultural change. In this context, it is vital to understand how design can contribute to the development of "cultural changing projects", innovating their practices, expanding its scope of action and considering "post materialist values", such as trust in oneself and the group, collaboration, self-esteem, self expression, among others.

Accordingly, the design extends its performance to the experiences that consumers have with objects, services, environments or with a mix of these products, and could be seen as an activity responsible for the design of systems and processes behind these experiences, from their philosophies to their final details [6].

ON THINGS THAT BRING BACK GOOD MEMORIES

Many things make us remember past pleasurable experiences and their accompanying emotions. Things, memory and emotions are so interlaced they hardly can be disentangled [5, 6, 9]. As observed by the neuroscientist António Damásio (1996) while times go by and we start reaching mature age, things around us start losing their "emotional innocence". According to the author, "it is very hard to imagine objects that are emotionally neutral". It is easy to agree that the older we get, the more experiences we go through, and the more material things around us gain special meaning and "emotional competence". Material things constitute the setting in which our life and memories take place and understanding why some of them become "memorable" was the starting point of the doctoral dissertation "Memory Artifacts of Everyday Life: an interdisciplinary view on things that bring back good memories".

One important phase of this study has been listening and registering stories about memorable things through qualitative research techniques such as group and individual discussions and semi-structured interviews with around 150 informants from different backgrounds. The results of this investigation has been based on these stories and interpreted within the theoretical framework of Memory Studies, an emerging interdisciplinary research field that includes disciplines and approaches concerning the complex relationship between memory, culture and society, as well as the influence of the past on present and future.

A major contribution for understanding why things bring back good memories has been provided by the French sociologist Maurice Halbwachs (1877-1945), recognize as the first scholar to treat memory as a collective and socially rooted fact in a time when memory was primarily understood as an individual phenomenon. For this reason and intellectual courage, Halbwachs is considered the father of the concept of "collective memory". In his posthumous book "La Mémoire Collective", the author demonstrated that we live and remember in society and based on material things. Halbwachs raises very interesting questions for designers, as illustrates his curious comparison of everyday objects to a silent and motionless society, indifferent to our agitation and change of mood and, as such, responsible for the transmission of the senses of order and quietude.

Halbwachs (1990) strengthens the idea that material things bring a sense of balance and stability examining a situation in which a small group suffers a shock: "Life around us continues as if nothing had happened (...) while we, our family, our friends feel as if a catastrophic wind were blowing". He concludes that peoples' indifference, as well as everything that is inert, can hurts but can also calm us down and gives us balance.

Halbwachs points out the existence of a strong relationship between people and those things that are familiar to them and emphasizes that the connection between social groups and the physical surroundings is a vital aspect of any group self-definition. He illustrates this statement describing how we feel when we find ourselves in an unfamiliar material environment: "before adapting to it, we go through a period of uncertainty, as if we had left behind our entire personality". Halbwachs adds: "usual images of the external world are inseparable from us".

The author wonders why do we become attached to some objects, disregarding comfort and aesthetics and answers his own question explaining: "our material surroundings carry our own marks and those of others at the same time. Our home, our furniture (...) reminds us of our family and our friends that we were used to seeing within that frame". In other words, the designed products that participate in our everyday lives end up becoming part of our identity and physical supports of our experiences, emotions and memories. By so being and depending on the quality of the experiences products promote or mediate, they can become support of pleasurable or unpleasant experiences and their associated emotions and memories.

In a rather curious passage, Halbwachs suggests that in order to see only the physical and formal qualities of things, we would have to adopt the attitude of physicists and artists. He claims that only under the "influence of painter's society" we would see things "not as they are, but rather as they are perceived by those who dedicate themselves exclusively to reproducing images".

Halbwachs concludes - after inviting the readers to go back in time as far as they can and as much as their thought can fixate on experiences preserved in their memory - that we will always find ourselves in places we know, we can locate and which are part of our material environment.

One of the main lessons this investigation learned from the Memory Studies was that the designed world memory and emotions are hardly intertwined. In this sense, designers can not “see only the physical and formal qualities of things”, but things as they are: expressions of our experiences, memories and emotions.

Another valuable contribution to this interdisciplinary study on things that bring back good memories came from the psychologist Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi and the anthropologist Eugene Rochberg-Halton's and their study (1981) of domestic objects and the process through which people construct meaning in family environments.

The origins of this well-known study, as described by Csikszentmihalyi (1995) in the article “Design & Order in Everyday Life”, were rooted in the author dissatisfaction with the vague and metaphorical accounts of how art affects the viewers as well as the notion that the purpose of art is to bring order to human experience. In this regard, the author conducted a study in which he interviewed members of families in the Chicago area to find out how ‘normal’ people responded to art objects and design qualities in their own environment. As he reports, the interviewees repeated impersonal phrases, showing emotional indifference to the works of art and suggesting that art doesn't play an important role in their lives. Although most homes have paintings and sculptures, these works did not appear to have any relation to the owners' psychological or spiritual sense. On the other hand, they demonstrated to have a strong attachment to domestic objects without any aesthetic value. From this observation, Csikszentmihalyi changed his research approach and began to ask which things were special to people and why. Together with the anthropologist Rochberg-Halton, he interviewed 315 people and 82 families, from different areas of the metropolitan region of

Chicago, always including the parents and, at least, one child and one of the grandparents. Describing some of the situations observed, Csikszentmihalyi explains the feeling of pride evoked in an interviewee by a plastic replica of the Venus de Milo, a gift from the company where she worked in recognition of her work as a salesman. According to the author, whenever the interviewee looked at the Venus replica, “she did not see the cheap goddess, but an image of herself as a capable, successful businessperson”.

The results of Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg - Halton's study showed that each house had “a network of objects that referred to meanings that gave sense to the lives of those who dwelt there” and that these meanings were rarely transmitted by works of art. According to the researchers, out of 1,694 objects identified as special, only 136 were graphic works, and 106 were sculptures, including the replica of the Venus de Milo. The great majority was valued for recalling a place, a person or a special event. Of these, a large proportion had been made by children, relatives and friends, which mean that their value also derived from the ties that bound the interviewees to the “authors” of the “works of art”. Csikszentmihalyi stresses that it wasn't the “aesthetic quality” of the objects that made them special, but “what the person did with it, and what the interaction meant to the person”.

In accordance with the findings of Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981), the stories of our informants about things that bring back good memories demonstrate that they remember what appears important to them and not what was presented to us as a sophisticated visual model. Based on these stories and on the above authors, among others from the field of Memory Studies and Contemporary Material Culture, we started to understand material things, including design products, as mediators and promoter of meaningful and purposeful social actions.

We realized, as well, that at least in our culture, things trigger good memories not because of the quality of their visual appearance or their “mechanical” performance, but the quality of social interactions, experiences and emotions they are associated with and their likely effects on individuals and society.

This study has identified a total of more than 300 artifacts, which were considered “memorable” by our informants, including flowers, pebbles, seashells, first milk tooth among other natural things used for several purposes. Both natural and man-made artifacts were organized into categories based on the reasons why they were considered memorable. As a result, eight main categories emerged from informants’ statements regarding (1) in which context their memory artifacts were acquired; (2) what and how they were used for; (3) which social actions they mediated or promoted; (4) who used them or with whom they were used; (5) which benefits they brought; (6) which effect, benefit or influence they had on informants’ life; (7) which emotions they evoke and (8) in which time of life they were used.

SOME POSSIBLE REASONS WHY SOME THINGS BRINGS GOOD MEMORIES AND PROMISING APPROACHES TO CREATE MEMORABLE PRODUCTS

According to the results of the above presented study, things bring back good memories when associated with the feelings of belonging, of duty and doing the things that need to be done, of betterment, of advancement of academic boundaries, of being safe, of being loved, of being recognized, with the sense of integrity, of dignity, with mental comfort and spiritual evolution and purpose. In short, and as presented above, the capacity of a product to trigger good memories - or its “memorability”, a social shaping factor related to ‘the quality of being worth remembering’ and inextricably intertwined to the actions products mediate and their effects on

individuals and society” (Damazio, 2009:146) - do not derived from their “mechanical”, but their “social” performance.

In resume, the artifacts of everyday life become memorable and bring back good memories when they are seen as a means of: (1) building and strengthening relationships; (2) being recognized and encouraged for our skills, attitudes and behaviors; (3) having fun and entertaining ourselves; (4) expressing and distinguishing ourselves; (5) comfortable mentally, physically and spiritually (6) making us feel loved and special.

In the same way, products become memorable when they are designed as a means of: (1) building and strengthening relationships; (2) being recognized and encouraged for our skills, attitudes and behaviors; (3) having fun and entertaining ourselves; (4) expressing and distinguishing ourselves; (5) comfortable mentally, physically and spiritually (6) making us feel loved and special.

Translating the above reasons in promising approaches to create memorable products:

Inspired by the findings of the study on “material emotional memory” and based on a investigation focusing contemporary design products as illustrates bellow, we arrived in the following six perspectives to Design in face of the Post Industrial Society’s needs: Design & Sociability or “Being Together” Design: Includes products that promote meaningful social interactions; strengthen relationships; improve living together; foster sharing and cooperation and serve as a means of living in harmony in a plural society.

This approach can be illustrated by Droog Dinner Delight 2005, by Marije Vogelzang, that has been designed around the theme of “sharing”. It included a curtain encircling the table with holes cut out for guests’ faces and arms, as well as plates cut in halves. For starters, guests received two servings of

Parma ham or two servings of melon and had to share one of their half plates to have a full meal (in:<http://www.droog.com/presentationsevents/droog-dinner-delight-2005/>).

Design & Citizenship or “Doing the Right Thing”

Design: Includes products that contribute to shape healthy and desirable social behaviors and practices; foster civility, enhance social responsibility; encourage humanitarian and inclusive attitudes and serve as a means of promoting the common good.

Some good examples of this approach are the projects developed by the Fun Theory campaign, sponsored by the Swedish Volkswagen. The central idea is to encourage people to change their behavior for the better in fun ways, “so you are not just rewarded with a good conscience, you also get a smile”. In the Piano Staircase project the steps on the stairs of a subway station were made to look like the keys of a piano. Whenever someone went up or down, each step played the sound of a musical note. The idea was to encourage people to take the stairs instead of the escalator (in: <http://www.thefuntheory.com>, 2011)

Design & Well-Being or “Relaxing” Design: Includes products that promote mental and physical wellness; relieve stress, tension and anxiety; bring the feelings of tranquility, calmness and serenity; renew mind, body and spirit and serve as a means of slowing down life’s rhythm. The example of this approach is the Alpha Sphere, by Sha, a Viennese artist and perception researcher, that created a multi-sensory experience combining form, color, light, sound, vibration and heat to reduce stress and bring deep relaxation.

(In:<http://www.alphasphere.at/content.asp?id=116&id2=0&id3=0&id4=0&lid=2&eid=1&sid=1&gid=0>)

Design & Self Expression | “Do as you wish” Design: Includes products that offer options to be adapted and

individualized by users according to their needs, wishes, preferences and imagination; enable users to have unique and self-expressive products. We illustrate this approach with the “Do Scratch Lamp”, created by Marti Guixe for Droog Design’s “Do create project and that is a black coated lamp that only shines where scratched. Its aim is to encourage the users to interact, play and intervene on the object’s final design.

(in: <http://www.droog.com/presentationsevents/do-create/do-design/>)

Design & Humor or “Having Fun” Design: Includes products that surprise, amuse, make people laugh, add joy to everyday life; turn routine tasks into enjoyable activities and serve as a means of bringing playful moments to life. The example is the Toast Messenger, by Sasha Tseng, that has a board to write messages that get “toasted” onto the bread. According to its designer: “It could improve a better relationship. (...). For kids, the cute comic on the toast is the best way to make them like to have an energetic breakfast. A beautiful morning begins in eating the message”. (In: <http://fotologue.jp/Sashapure#/3678269/4676403>)

Design & Self-Steem or “Making Fell Good” Design: Includes products that contributes to enhance self-esteem, self-confidence and self-motivation and to bring sick and suffering users a sense of purpose, inner strength and a positive outlook on life. To illustrate this approach we bring the touching film that registered the planned event by the European bus company Arriva as part of 'I want a better bus ride' campaign of the birthday celebration and homage to the somalian bus driver Mukhtar. (in:<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xgOyTNtsWYy>)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Our studies on Design, Memory and Emotion have been greatly contributing to our understanding of how products affect our everyday life and shape our behaviors and practices, reflect our beliefs and values

and become inseparable from what we are and what we remember (they are also helping us to understand that remembering and using things are social processes and always include the other, be it physically or mentally).

They confirm, in addition, that products function within social contexts and mediate most of our actions, linking people to each other and to their everyday life. Our findings also suggest that designers create and give physical form to products, while users put them in action and give them social form, extending their functions and meanings far beyond those for which they were designed. As Arjun Appadurai [1] teaches, products have a social life and “their meanings are inscribed in their forms, their uses, their trajectories”. The anthropologist adds that it is not merely things but “things-in-motion that illuminate their human and social context”.

In this context, we can say that products have a history of their own related to the social actions, experiences, emotions and transformations they are involved with and have no meanings aside from those attributed to them by their users. We can, consequently, say that the goal of Design shall be to create products that turn themselves into memorable things, not only for the quality of their tangible properties, but mainly for the quality of their “social transformation properties”.

As suggested by Vera Damazio (2009:146) inspired in Norberto Bobbio’s formulation that we are what we remember, we better have good things to remember. Taking into account the above considerations, we reinforce the proposal that designers have to “expand their focus to product memorability, or, as defined above, to the quality of being worth remembering and that is deeply associated with the quality of the social actions, effects and transformations products mediate (Damazio, 2009:146). In doing so, designers would not design “toys”, but imagine how to promote the

action of playing and the sense of enjoyment. They would not think in “didactic tools”, but, rather, in the action of learning and the sense of advancement of academic boundaries. In other words, designers would focus on actions, feelings and behaviors - rather than products - as, for example “helping children overcome fear of darkness”, “breastfeeding comfortably”, “relieving stress and tension” “connecting people”, “having fun”, “reinforcing and building one’s self-esteem”, “respecting differences”, among other positive effects on users. Designing for “showing respect”, for “relaxing”, for “cultivating healthy attitudes”, “increasing sociability”, “promoting solidarity”, “rediscovering slowness and permitting attention to the important things in life” and all vital aspects of our humanness, may rise new and original questions and also generate new and original solutions.

All we need in post industrial times.

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